

DEVELOPING COMPONENT-SCALE HIERARCHICAL COMPOSITES USING NANOCARBONS

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ABSTRACT

Much attention has been given to the development of nanocomposite and hierarchical composite materials in recent times, for the enhancement of mechanical and multi-functional properties. Despite many promising results the issues of repeatability and scale-up have yet to be adequately addressed, with manufacture limited to small lab-scale samples. In this work we explore techniques for component-scale manufacture of hierarchical composites by liquid infusion, using both carbon nanotube and graphene materials. A unique plasma process, developed by Haydale Ltd., was adopted for controllable functionalization of large batches of nanocarbons (100s of grams) prior to mixing with epoxy resin. A rheological study indicated that filler morphology, functionalization and fill weight all have an effect on epoxy resin viscosity. Using these developed nanocomposite resins a resin infusion under flexible tooling (RIFT) technique was developed. Resin flow studies informed an optimum setup that facilitated full wet-out of large area UD carbon fibre laminates and the resulting materials showed significant improvements in mechanical properties, demonstrating up to ~50% increase in compression after impact (CAI) properties. The RIFT process and tooling were further developed to enable the manufacture of I-section stiffeners and the production of component-scale (0.9x0.55m) stiffened panels was demonstrated.

1 INTRODUCTION

The phenomenal properties reported for nanocarbons such as carbon nanotubes and graphenes have generated much interest for their use in composite materials. Theoretical predictions demonstrate the potential for significant improvements in strength, stiffness and multi-functionality of materials. However, the theoretically predicted properties are rarely achieved in practice and in some cases reduction in properties have been reported [1, 2]. The variability observed is related to a number of key challenges in the production of nanocomposites, namely the de-agglomeration of the nanomaterials, their dispersion within a matrix material (such as epoxy) and the adhesion between the nanomaterials and the surrounding matrix material. The inherently low surface energy of nanocarbons means they do not interact well with other materials and large agglomerates tend to form due to relatively high Van der Waals forces. It is therefore necessary to alter the surface chemistry of nanocarbons, known as functionalization, in order to enhance their interaction with a matrix material. It is the variability in functionalization, mixing and manufacturing approaches adopted that results in the wide range of results observed in the literature.

Commonly wet chemistry approaches are used to achieve functionalization, whereby strong acid solutions are used to oxidize nanocarbons, disrupting carbon-carbon bonds and attaching functional chemical groups at the resulting defect sites. Ultrasonication is normally used during this process to promote de-agglomeration and dispersion. Both of these processes are very difficult to control and optimize, and have been shown to damage the structure of nanocarbons [3]. Not only are these processes limited to small quantities of nanocarbons, only a few grams, they require significant additional processing steps and produce harmful waste. An alternative approach to functionalization is the use of plasma. It has been shown that plasma can be used to covalently functionalize nanocarbons [4] and Haydale Ltd. have developed a unique plasma process that can carefully control the applied functionalization by varying the gas type and plasma processing parameters. The process is dry, energy efficient and scalable. Multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNT) processed using Haydale's plasma treatment have demonstrated improved dispersion in epoxy resin [5] and in previous work the authors of this paper have demonstrated up to 10% improvements in the flexural strength of epoxy resin using plasma processed MWCNTs, graphene nanoplatelets (GNP) and few layer graphene (FLG) [6].

To produce a hierarchical material, a nanoreinforced resin must be combined with more traditional macro-scale carbon fibre reinforcement. Both closed mould liquid infusion techniques, such as RTM, and open mould techniques, such as resin infusion under flexible tooling (RIFT), sometimes referred to as vacuum assisted resin transfer moulding (VARTM), have proved popular because they are cost effective and allow flexibility of resin selection and mixing. Reported samples sizes produced have been relatively small, in the order of 0.2x0.2m [7], due to the increased viscosity observed with the addition of nano-fillers, the difficulty in producing large batch sizes and the low permeability of carbon fibres limiting the maximum flow distance achievable.

This work aims to address the scalability in functionalization, mixing and resin infusion composite manufacture. A unique plasma treatment process was used to give chemical functionalization to MWCNTs and few layer graphene (FLG), in a dry and scalable process. A rheological study was undertaken to investigate the effects of filler morphology and functionalization chemistry on the viscosity of nanofilled resins. Resins filled with 0.5wt% MWCNT and FLG were used in the development of resin infusion manufacturing approaches for component-scale hierarchical composites. The manufacturing techniques demonstrated significant improvements in compression after impact (CAI) strength (~50%) samples from MWCNT and FLG reinforced hierarchical composites and stiffened panels, representative of an aerospace structure, were manufactured with dimensions of 0.55x0.9m.

2 NANOFILLED RESINS

Three nanocarbon morphologies were selected for use in this work: multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNT), graphene nanoplatelets (GNP) and few layer graphene (FLG). The materials were supplied by Haydale Ltd. and their properties have been characterised and are presented in Table 1.

Property	MWCNT	GNP	FLG	Method
Surface area	70-80 m ² /g	25 m ² /g	>700 m ² /g	BET
Bulk density	190 kg/m ³	215 kg/m ³	200-400 kg/m ³	EN ISO 60
Shape	tube	Large flat area	Small flat area	SEM
Long aspect dimension	~1 µm	0.3-5µm	0.3-2µm	SEM
Short aspect dimension	~15-30 nm	<50 nm	<10 nm	SEM

Table 1: Nanomaterial properties

Sika Biresin CR83 infusion resin and medium speed hardener (CH83-6) were chosen as the base resin system. This resin system was selected due to its very low viscosity (<200 mPas), long pot life (up to 180 mins) and room temperature curing. The low viscosity and long pot life are important for two reasons. Firstly the aim of this work was to resin infuse large-scale UD carbon fibre laminates that have low permeability and are therefore challenging to achieve full wet out. Secondly the addition of nanofillers was expected to increase the base resin viscosity making liquid infusion more difficult.

To assess the effect of filler morphology on the base resin viscosity, three batches of filled resins were prepared containing 1wt% of either MWCNT, GNP or FLG plasma treated with a carboxylic functionalization. To assess the effect of functionalization on the base resin viscosity MWCNT were plasma treated with carboxylic, oxygen and amine functionalization and mixed at 1wt% with the CR83 resin. In all cases the nanofillers were hand mixed as a dry powder directly into the CR83 resin at 5wt% and once combined high shear mixing was used to further enhance dispersion. The required fill weights were then achieved by dilution with additional resin and further mixing.

The viscosity of the base resin and the six nanofilled resins were assessed using Bohlin Gemini HR nano rotational rheometer. A cone diameter of 40mm was used with a 4° angle and the shear rate was varied from 1 – 100 1/s. Figure 1 shows the results for the as purchased resin and those filled with 1wt% MWCNT, GNP and FLG with carboxylic functionalization. It can be seen that morphology has a significant effect on viscosity. The addition of MWCNTs increased the viscosity considerably, whereas the graphene morphologies (GNP and FLG) had no discernible effect compared with the as purchased resin. The MWCNTs demonstrate shear thinning, with a reduction in viscosity at higher shear rates, whereas the as purchased and graphene filled resins demonstrate Newtonian behaviour. This is an important result when considering nanofilled resins for liquid infusion because keeping the viscosity low is essential to ensuring efficient and complete wet out of a fibre stack. Figure 2 presents the rheometry results for the as purchased resin and resins filled with 1wt% MWCNTs that have been plasma treated with carboxylic, oxygen and amine functionalizations. The viscosity increases in all three cases when compared with the as purchased resin, however the extent of increase is dependent on the functionalization applied. The carboxylic (COOH) functionalization demonstrates the greatest increase in viscosity and the oxygen functionalization demonstrates the smallest increase. Higher viscosities are attributed to improved interfacial interactions between the MWCNTs and the polymer resin. Similar effects have been observed by Kim et al [8], who demonstrated improvements in dispersion and corresponding increases in viscosity through the functionalization of MWCNTs.

The MWCNT and FLG nanocarbon morphologies were selected for hierarchical composite development due to their higher specific surface area (Table 1) which will allow greater interaction with the epoxy matrix. The carboxylic plasma functionalization was chosen for both nanocarbons due to the demonstrated improvements in interfacial interaction with the selected resin matrix system (Figure 1). Although the carboxylic functionalization causes the greatest increase in viscosity, this is thought to be outweighed by the greater interfacial interaction.

Figure 1: Rheology results for differing morphologies

Figure 2: Rheology results for differing functionalization

3 RESIN INFUSION DEVELOPMENT

The resins used to develop a resin infusion manufacturing approach for hierarchical composites were 0.5wt% MWCNT and 0.5% FLG with a carboxylic functionalization. The reinforcement used was a 200gsm UD carbon fibre supplied by Formax (FCIM312). This material is designed for resin infusion applications with a small amount of polyethylene transverse stitching (equivalent to 3gsm) to hold the material in sheet form and enhance through thickness permeability. A 16 ply quasi-isotropic layup was used and a series of propagation studies were undertaken on samples of 80mm x 250mm, as shown in Figure 3. In this setup the first inlet was placed at the left edge, the second inlet was placed at 100mm from the first and the vacuum outlet was placed at the right hand end. The resin infusion trials were undertaken on a glass mould surface, such that the propagation of the top and bottom resin fronts could be monitored. Figure 4 and 5 present the distance of the resin flow front from the first inlet versus time for the as purchased resin and the FLG filled resin, respectively. The time is measured from the point at which resin flowed into inlet 1 and once the resin front reached the second inlet the first was closed and the second opened. It can be seen that following initial rapid flow the resin front on the top surface soon slows and as expected the resin front on the bottom surface lags behind. Interestingly, despite demonstrating no observable increase in viscosity the FLG filled resin exhibited a slower flow rate. This indicates that there may be some filtering effects occurring that restrict resin flow. The results demonstrate that it is possible to infuse a quasi-isotropic layup of UD fibres with both as purchased and nanofilled resins and that the sequential inlets have the potential to facilitate the infusion of larger areas. The sequential inlet approach also has the benefit of limiting pressure differential across the mould, therefore limiting the variation in material thickness. Based on these results a resin inlet spacing of 80mm was selected for future manufacture in order to ensure good wet out and to reduce infusion time.

Figure 3: Resin infusion trial setup

Figure 4: Resin flow distance versus time for as purchased resin

Figure 5: Resin flow distance versus time for 0.5% FLG-COOH filled resin

4 COMPRESSION AFTER IMPACT PROPERTIES

Three 550x180mm panels were manufactured from a 16 ply quasi-isotropic fibre layup using resin infusion with as purchased, 0.5wt% MWCNT filled and 0.5% FLG filled resins. The panels were infused across the short dimension using three sequential resin inlets spaced at 80mm and post manufacture C-scan inspection showed the panels to have good uniformity. Five 100x150mm CAI samples were cut from each panel. The CAI samples were subject to a 10J impact at their center using an Instron 9250HV impact test machine, prior to C-scan inspection and compression testing to failure in accordance with British Standard BS ISO 18352:2009. Table 2 presents the CAI results for all three sets of samples, including the delamination area and the CAI strength. The average delamination area after impact was similar for the materials manufactured with as purchased resin and the FLG filled resin, whereas the MWCNT filled material showed a significant increase. Both the nanoreinforced materials demonstrated a significant improvement in average CAI strength compared with the as purchased resin. The FLG reinforced material demonstrated the greatest improvement, with nearly 50% increase in residual strength. The smaller improvement (~28%) observed for MWCNT reinforcement is a result of the larger delamination area experienced in this material.

These results demonstrate that hierarchical composites manufactured by resin infusion exhibit significant increases in the CAI strength compared with standard composites. This is an important result because CAI strength is often a limiting design case for composite materials in aerospace applications. The observed performance of these hierarchical composites is above that which would be expected based on the previously reported properties of the filled resins [6]. Further work is required

to understand the mechanism for the observed reinforcement but two hypotheses have been suggested. 1) There is a synergistic interaction between the two scales of reinforcement, i.e. the macro-scale fibres and the nano-scale particles, that enhances the reinforcement effect. 2) The observed filtering effect (Figure 5) prevents larger agglomerates from entering the fibre stack, resulting in a higher quality hierarchical composite with only individual particles and small agglomerates reinforcing the polymer matrix.

Material	Average delamination area after impact (mm²)	CAI strength σ_{CAI} (MPa)
100% CR83 Resin	1010.2 \pm 280.7	121.0 \pm 12.5
0.5% MWCNT COOH	1338.8 \pm 296.1	154.5 \pm 11.8
0.5% FLG700 COOH	1091.2 \pm 127.9	180.9 \pm 7.9

Table 2: Compression after impact results

5 COMPONENT-SCALE PANEL MANUFACTURE

The scalability of the plasma functionalization, resin mixing and resin infusion processes has been demonstrated by the manufacture of component-scale stiffened panels, representative of a wing skin, using FLG filled resin. An 8kg batch of 0.5wt% FLG COOH filled resin was produced and used for panel manufacture. Figure 6 shows an image of a completed hierarchical composite panel. The skin and I-section stiffeners were manufactured separately using resin infusion and then bonded together. The overall dimensions are 550x900mm and four stiffeners were attached to each panel. Post manufacture C-scan inspection of stiffener webs and the skin sections showed the materials to be of good quality. The skin sections were manufactured using ten sequential resin inlets as per the approach described in section 4. A semi-closed mould technique was developed to infuse the I-section stiffeners in two infusion stages.

6 CONCLUSIONS

Techniques for the scale up of hierarchical composites have been successfully developed and demonstrated. The use of a scalable and energy efficient plasma treatment has been used to functionalize and improve the dispersion of nanocarbons in an epoxy resin. Combined with a high shear mixing process large batches (8kg) of nanofilled resin were produced. A sequential inlet resin infusion approach was developed that facilitated the manufacture of component-scale stiffened panels representative of real aerospace structures. The manufactured hierarchical composites have been shown to produce significant improvements (up to 50%) in CAI strength when compared with traditional composite materials. This work has demonstrated exciting potential for the development of novel lightweight hierarchical composites with improved mechanical properties and industrial scalability for use in aerospace applications.

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Figure 6: Component-scale hierarchical composite panel manufactured with 0.5wt% FLG COOH filled resin

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